

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF PROCESSING INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

¹S.N.Khashimova

²A.A.Abdikarimova

Tashkent State Technical University

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000793>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th May 2023

Accepted: 30th May 2023

Online: 31th May 2023

KEY WORDS

Recycling industry, innovation, developing, new technologies, diversification, competitiveness.

ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to the role of recycling industry over the Uzbekistan's economy and there is mentioned its directions of innovative developments.

At present, in Uzbekistan is actively promoted innovation development of all sectors of the economy. It is caused by importance of the tasks on "Increase of competitiveness of the national economy due to deepening of structural transformations, modernization and diversification of its leading industries" Action Strategy on the five priority areas for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021.

Manufacturing is the basis for sustainable growth economy of Uzbekistan.

Manufacturing- an industry that uses agricultural products (cotton, wool, etc.) or industrial products (oil, natural gas, ore, etc.) as raw materials. Manufacturing produces both capital goods and commodities.

In manufacturing, the following industries are distinguished:

- ferrous metallurgy
- non-ferrous metallurgy
- chemical and petrochemical industry
- engineering and metalworking
- forest, woodworking and pulp and paper industry
- building materials industry
- glass industry and porcelain and faience industry
- light industry
- food industry
- microbiological industry
- medical industry
- printing industry

Countries with a well- developed manufacturing sector produce high- technology products that use resource-efficient technologies to leverage natural and human resources and increase labor productivity.

The higher share of manufacturing implies a higher degree of diversification of the economy, therefore a higher degree of sustainability.

According to World Bank data, the percentage of manufacturing in GPD has averaged about 23.6% over the past two decades in upper-middle income countries, 18.1% globally and 9.9% in Uzbekistan.

In the Republic as a whole, reserves of the growth of the manufacturing industry are estimated at about 6.4% to 17.7%. Their use would significantly improve the structure of the economy and macroeconomic performance and create a significant number of new productive and sustainable jobs.

In the most of researches the manufacturing industry looks at the enterprise level, and the work analyzed at the macro level, identifying the factors influencing its growth, is very few.

From an environmental point of view, the natural tendency of enterprises is to seek efficient ways of using resources, as entrepreneurs seek to maximize profits and minimize costs by innovating in technological processes. This leads to resource conservation, reduced pollution and recycling.

The human factor, investment support for R&D, innovation play an important role in the development of manufacturing industry and, consequently, in inclusive economic growth.

In Uzbekistanis adopted the direction of economic growth in building an innovative economy. Measures have been developed within the framework of the Strategy for the five development priorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021.

It can be concluded that relatively stable growth has been achieved in terms of the number of marketing and technological innovations. In 2018, 5.9 times more innovations were introduced than in 2009. As for the costs for them, here we observe an increase over this period by 10.5 times. Unfortunately, since 2014, the number of invention patents received has begun to decrease, which once again confirms the relevance of the development of innovative activity in the industrial sector of the economy (Table 1).

Table 1

Industry Innovation Indicators for 2009-2018

Years	Industrial innovations (marketing and technological), <i>piece</i>	Number of employees R&D, <i>people</i>	Expenses for marketing and technological innovations, mln som	Industrial patents and inventions, <i>piece</i>
2009	231	220	276313,8	37
2010	243	171	265228,4	37
2011	301	108	367401,0	35
2012	274	114	271652,4	21
2013	684	165	3123516,8	25
2014	872	104	3258026,8	18

2015	855	98	5524566,6	11
2016	959	103	1210045,5	8
2017	1177	133	1919747,1	6
2018	1379	145	2900828,4	2

¹Based on information from the State Statistics Committee

In today's world, innovation has a leading role in the development of society. They are the basis of economic growth and provide the foundation for business competitiveness growth in the market. As a source of productivity, profitability and competitiveness, innovation is a commercialized, radical improvement. Innovative activity of economic entities is inextricably associated with their innovative development. Innovative development consists in activation of innovation activity of enterprise and development of its innovation potential. Innovation activity, in turn, is related to the transformation of the results of scientific activity in management, a new or improved product sold on the market, or the process introduced characterizes resource B production. Innovative capabilities of the subject allowing him to carry out innovative activities.

Innovative development of an enterprise is a key to increase of efficiency of its activity and a necessary condition for ensuring sustainability and success of its operation in the long term.

In the modern world, the main directions of innovative development of economic entities are considered:

- development of new technologies;
- electronic production;
- chemical and electrification;
- introduction of new materials, including secondary processing of raw materials;
- complex mechanization and automation, etc.

Learning HOBLIX technologies helps to solve many production and socio-economic problems. Their introduction into production processes can increase the volume of finished products without involving additional factors of production. Examples include the development of biotechnology, which provides solutions to commodity and food problems.

Electronic production involves the provision of high-performance electronics to all structures of the enterprise, ranging from personal computers to satellite communications and information systems. In the modern world, against the background of total informatization of public systems, the spread of computer technologies and the development of Internet networks play a decisive role in innovation processes.

The creation of the introduction of new materials, characterized by qualitatively new effective properties (such as corrosion and radiation resistance, superconductivity, heat resistance, etc.), can increase the competitiveness of manufactured products, which positively affects the profitability of the enterprise.

¹ Based on information from the State Statistics Committee

One of the most important indicators of innovation development is considered its effectiveness, which is determined by the ratio of the resulting effect and the costs necessary to achieve it. The effect of innovation development in this case refers to the result of scientific and technical activities. At the enterprise level, it is reflected in profits.

At present, innovative development distinguishes four basic types of effects:

- technical effects associated with the emergence of new inventions, techniques and technologies, know-how, innovation proposals, etc.;
- resource effects based on the release of resources to enterprises (financial, labor, material);
- economic effects reflected in the growth of labor productivity, profit and profitability, as well as reduced labor intensity, material consumption and production cost;
- the effects of the social order are associated with an increase in the material and cultural standard of living of the population, better satisfaction of human needs, increased safety and social improvement of working conditions.

Bringing such effects into a measurable, often cost-effective, form allows comparing them with the costs of obtaining such results. The greater the difference between the effect and the cost of causing it, the higher efficiency of innovative development of the enterprise.

Being a relative value, the efficiency of innovation development is measured in percentages or fractions of a unit and characterizes the result of the costs incurred. The main criterion of efficiency is maximization of profit (effect) at set costs, or minimization of costs necessary for achieving a given effect.

Priority directions of innovative development of manufacturing industry are:

- complex use and deep processing of local resources up to the production of finished products in demand on the world and domestic markets;
- expansion of localized production;
- increasing the competitiveness of industries;
- to promote the development of new branches of high-tech industry;
- improvement of the institutional structures needed to foster innovation.

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